

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Medium- to long- term prediction of priority weeds for management

SPOKE 6 - PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY

Flagship Project VINO

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, and demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the analyses performed to assess relationships between biotic/abiotic edaphic factors and the occurrence of glyphosate resistance in weeds identified in the vineyards that have been visited during summer 2023.

This analysis can provide useful tools for medium- and long-term prediction of priority weeds for management due to their ability to develop resistance to glyphosate.

A) Analysis of physical-chemical soil factors

Report about analysis of the physical-chemical properties of vineyards soils in relation to resistance occurrence.

Glyphosate resistant weeds surveyed in the vineyards of Oltrepò Pavese

Seven wine-growing farms in Oltrepò Pavese were visited during summer 2023: 4 managed according to the Directive EC 2009/128 (Farm 2,4,5,6) and 3 performing organic agriculture according to Regulation EU 2018/848 (Farm 1,3,7). Farms were signed with an identification code (i.e. Farm1, Farm2, etc...). (Figure 1).

Figure 1: distribution of the visited grapevine farms in Oltrepò Pavese

The visited farms and the management practices applied in the vineyards are listed in table 1.

Table 1: list of the farms with the management practices applied in the vineyards

Farm	Agricultural management	Management practices applied in vineyards
Farm 1	Reg. EU 2018/848 Organic	tillage
Farm 2	Dir. EC 2009/128	subsoil tillage
Farm 3	Reg. EU 2018/848 Organic	spontaneous grass cover
Farm 4	Dir. EC 2009/128	subsoil tillage
Farm 5	Dir. EC 2009/128	subsoil tillage
Farm 6	Dir. EC 2009/128	tillage
Farm 7	Reg. EU 2018/848 Organic	tillage + cover crop (<i>Leguminosae</i>)

At the 4 farms managed according to the Directive EC 2009/128, a total of 4 weed species have been recorded in the vineyards by winegrowers as able to survive the treatment with glyphosate: *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) P. Beauv, *Sorghum halepense* (L.) Pers., *Conyza canadensis* Cronq and

Cynodon dactylon (L.) Pers (Figure 2). The same plant species were surveyed in the vineyards of the organic farms¹.

Figure 2: glyphosate-resistant weeds surveyed in the vineyards of Oltrepò Pavese

Following controlled growth and herbicide application trials performed in collaboration with SAGEA® Group company, Assay Centre offering services in the areas of Research and Experimentation in Agriculture and Environmental Fields, all the previous reported weeds exhibited resistance toward glyphosate application (details about methods and results are reported in Milestone 5.5 and Deliverable 5.5).

¹ Organic farms were used as “control sample” to be compared to those applying Dir. EC 2009/128 principles, in order to identify weeds that could be used as theoretical "susceptible" to be tested with resistant samples (details about methods and results are reported in Milestone 5.5 and Deliverable 5.5).

Analysis of the physical and chemical characteristics of soils and of the relationship with glyphosate resistance occurrence

Soil sampling

At each visited farm, soil samples have been aseptically collected from 10 to 25 cm depth following the “X non-systematic soil sampling method” by Lambkin et al. (2004) from: 1) a vineyard where *E. crus-galli*, *S. halepense*, *C. canadensis* and *C. dactylon* were surveyed; 2) a non-tilled and not cultivated field near the vineyard².

Analysis of the physical and chemical properties of soil

For all the samples of soil, physical and chemical properties were analyzed by the laboratory “Minoprio Analisi e Certificazioni” (Como, Italy) according to the Italian standard protocols (DM 13/09/99). The following parameters were evaluated: soil texture (soil composition in coarse and fine sand, silt and clay as g/kg s.s.), pH of H₂O and pH of CaCl₂, total acidity, total limestone (CaCO₃) as g/kg s.s., total and organic carbon (C and C_{org}) and organic matter as g/kg s.s., total nitrogen (N) as g/kg s.s., C/N ratio, exchangeable calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), potassium (K) and sodium (Na) as meq/100g s.s., cation exchange capacity (CEC) as meq/100g s.s., base saturation percentage (BS), Ca/Mg and Mg/K ratios, exchangeable sodium percentage (exNa), extractable phosphorus (P) as mg/kg s.s. and humidity percentage (Hum).

Data processing

In order to visually represent the physical and chemical properties of soils and to classify soil samples according to the similarity of these data, a heatmap and a hierarchical clustering (“Manhattan” distance – “Ward.D2” algorithm) were computed by R software (R Core Team).

The cluster analysis splits the samples into 2 main clusters (Figure 3). Cluster A is split into two sub-clusters: sub-cluster A.1 includes more acidic soils with a high content of organic carbon, organic matter and nitrogen (N) and phosphorous (P), high base saturation rate (BS), high Ca/Mg

² These soil samples were used as “control sample” to be compared to that of the vineyard, in order to track possible differences in the microbial composition or in the soil texture and chemistry due to the treatments applied (tillage and grapevine cultivation).

ratio, high exchangeable sodium percentage (exNa); sub-cluster A.2 joint together soils characterized by a high content of clay, alkaline pH, high content of Ca, Mg, K and Na, high cation exchange capacity (CEC) and high humidity rate. Cluster B includes soils characterized by a coarse texture, an alkaline pH of H₂O and CaCl₂ and a low concentration of organic carbon, organic matter, Ca, Mg, K, Na and P. The hierarchical classification does not distinguish either between land use systems, nor between the agricultural management applied, since no grouping is shown in this sense.

Figure 3: Heatmap and hierarchical clustering (“Manhattan” distance and “ward.D2” algorithm) computed on physical and chemical properties of soils. Darker the color, higher the value of the respective variable. ORG: farm performing organic agriculture according to Regulation EU 2018/848; EC128: farm managed according to the Directive EC 2009/128.

Analysis of the relationship between the physical and chemical properties of soil and the presence of glyphosate-resistant weeds

In order to identify the most distinctive physical and chemical properties in the analyzed soils and test eventual relationships with the occurrence of herbicide resistance, principal component analyses (PCAs) were computed by R software (R Core Team). The following analyses consider only the vineyards of farms where glyphosate-resistant and glyphosate-susceptible weeds biotypes have been identified.

PCA of figure 4, that considers the physical and chemical properties of vineyard's soils and the presence of glyphosate-resistant and glyphosate-susceptible *E. crus-galli* biotypes, does not suggest any relationship between the considered variables.

Figure 4: PCA of the physical and chemical properties of soils. Brown arrows indicate the most contributive variables to data disposition in the chart: darker the brown, major the contribution. Red points (RES): soils where glyphosate-resistant biotypes of *E. crus-galli* were identified. Green points (SUS): soils where glyphosate-susceptible biotypes of *E. crus-galli* were identified. Cos2: the squared cosine, showing the importance of each component for a given observation; it is useful to find the components that are important for interpreting data; higher the cos2 value, major the contribution of the variable (Abdi, H. and Williams, L.J. (2010).

The PCA of figure 5, that considers the physical and chemical properties of soils and the presence of glyphosate-resistant *S. halepense* biotypes, suggests an association of resistance occurrence with the alkaline pH of H₂O and CaCl₂ and a high content of K.

Figure 5: PCA of the physical and chemical properties of soils. Brown arrows indicate the most contributive variables to data disposition in the chart: darker the brown, major the contribution. Red points (RES): soils where glyphosate-resistant biotypes of *S. halepense* were identified. Green points (SUS): soils where glyphosate-susceptible biotypes of *S. halepense* were identified. Cos2: The squared cosine, showing the importance of each component for a given observation; it is useful to find the components that are important for interpreting data; higher the cos2 value, major the contribution of the variable (Abdi, H. and Williams, L.J. (2010).

The PCA of figure 6 aligns with that shown in figure 5, reflecting the association of glyphosate-resistance occurrence in *C. canadensis* with the alkaline pH of H₂O and CaCl₂ and the high content of K in the soils. Moreover, the PCA shows a relationship between the texture and the chemistry of soils, and the agricultural management applied, similar to that of figure 5.

Figure 6: PCA of the physical and chemical properties of soils. Brown arrows indicate the most contributive variables to data disposition in the chart: darker the brown, major the contribution. Red points (RES): soils where glyphosate-resistant biotypes of *C. canadensis* were identified. Green points (SUS): soils where glyphosate-susceptible biotypes of *C. canadensis* were identified. Cos2: The squared cosine, showing the importance of each component for a given observation; it is useful to find the components that are important for interpreting data; higher the cos2 value, major the contribution of the variable (Abdi, H. and Williams, L.J. (2010).

The PCA of figure 6, that considers the physical and chemical properties of soils and the presence of glyphosate-resistant and glyphosate-susceptible *C. dactylon* biotypes, suggests a relationship between the texture and the chemistry of soils and the agricultural management applied, similar to that of figure 5. Besides, the presence of glyphosate-resistant *C. dactylon* biotypes seems to be associated with an alkaline pH, high humidity %, high cation exchange capacity (CEC) and high content of Mg.

Figure 6: PCA of the physical and chemical properties of soils. Brown arrows indicate the most contributive variables to data disposition in the chart: darker the brown, major the contribution. Red points (RES): soils where glyphosate-resistant biotypes of *C. dactylon* were identified. Green points (SUS): soils where glyphosate-susceptible biotypes of *C. dactylon* were identified. Cos2: The squared cosine, showing the importance of each component for a given observation; it is useful to find the components that are important for interpreting data; higher the cos2 value, major the contribution of the variable (Abdi, H. and Williams, L.J. (2010).

B) Analysis of soil microbiome

Report about analysis of the microbial composition and diversity of vineyard soils in relation to resistance occurrence.

Analysis of soil microbial composition

Total DNA was extracted from soil samples. Metagenomic amplicons of bacterial, archaeal and fungal communities were obtained following PCR amplification, using primers linked to Illumina adapters. To produce bacterial and archaeal amplicons, the V3-V4 hypervariable region of the prokaryotic 16S rRNA gene was targeted. To obtain fungal amplicons the ribosomal ITS2 region was targeted. Sequencing and bioinformatic taxonomical analyses were conducted by BMR Genomics srl (Padua, Italy). Relative abundance of all microbial taxa at the taxonomic rank of orders was considered and statistical analysis was performed using R software (R Core Team).

Data processing

In order to visually represent the microbial communities' composition of soils at the rank of order and to classify soil samples according to the similarity of these data, a heatmap and a hierarchical clustering ("Manhattan" distance – "Ward.D2" algorithm) were computed by R software (R Core Team). Only microbial taxa recording a relative abundance $\geq 2\%$ were considered.

Figure 7: Heatmap and hierarchical clustering ("Manhattan" distance and "ward.D2" algorithm) computed microbial communities' composition of soils. The darker the color, the higher the abundance of the respective order is. ORG: farm performing organic agriculture according to Regulation EU 2018/848; EC128: farm managed according to the Directive EC 2009/128.

The hierarchical classification (figure 7) does not distinguish between different agricultural management techniques, but groups together the majority of soils collected from non-cultivated fields, differentiating them from vineyard soils, showing that microbial composition is influenced by land use.

In fact, the cluster analysis of soils split the samples into 2 main clusters. Cluster A includes all soil samples collected in non-cultivated fields of farms 1, 3, 4, 5 and 6. Cluster B includes all the other soils and is split into sub-cluster B.1, including only soils collected in vineyards of farms 1, 3, 4, 5 and 6. Sub-cluster B.2 includes soil collected in farms 2 and 7 either from vineyards and from non-cultivated fields. Soil microbial consortia of non-cultivated fields of cluster A are characterized by the presence of Chitinophagales, Opitutales, Polyangiales and Microascales. Soil microbial consortia of vineyards of sub-cluster B.1 are characterized by the presence of Viciniabacterales, Pyrinomonadales and Filobasidiales. Soil microbial consortia of sub-cluster B.2 are characterized by the presence of Micrococcales, Bacillales, Capnodiales and Rhizophlyctidales.

Analysis of relationship between soil microbial composition and the presence of glyphosate-resistant weeds

In order to identify the most distinctive orders of bacteria, *Archaea* and fungi in the analyzed soils and to explore their relationship with the occurrence of herbicide resistance, principal component analyses (PCAs) were computed by R software (R Core Team).

The following analyses consider only the vineyards of farms where glyphosate-resistant and glyphosate-susceptible weeds biotypes have been identified.

In general, results show different microbial profiles in vineyard soils where glyphosate resistance was detected compared to organic farm vineyards where no herbicide treatment was carried out.

The PCA in Figure 8 suggests that soils in which glyphosate-resistant *E. crus-galli* biotypes are present, are characterized by a microbial profile with high abundance values of Gemmatimonadales, Pedosphaerales, Rokubacteriales, Saccharomycetales and Haliangiales and Dothideomycetes. In the soils where glyphosate-susceptible *E. crus-galli* biotypes were identified high abundance values of Capnodiales, Cyanobacteriales, Pezizales, Myxococcales, Sphingobacteriales, Bacillales and Cytophagales are recorded.

Figure 8: PCA of the microbial communities' composition of soils. Blue arrows indicate the most contributive variables to data disposition in the chart: darker the blue, major the contribution. Red points (RES): soils where glyphosate-resistant biotypes of *E. crus-galli* were identified. Green points (SUS): soils where glyphosate-susceptible biotypes of *E. crus-galli* were identified. Cos2: The squared cosine, showing the importance of each component for a given observation; it is useful to find the components that are important for interpreting data; higher the cos2 value, major the contribution of the variable (Abdi, H. and Williams, L.J. (2010).

The PCA in Figure 9 shows that soils in which glyphosate-resistant *S. halepense* biotypes were identified, are characterized by a microbial profile with high abundance values of Ktedonobacterales, Dothideomycetes (Incertae sedis), Micromonosporales, Pedosphaerales and Gaiellales. In the soils where glyphosate-susceptible *S. halepense* biotypes were identified, the microbial profile is characterized by the prevalence of Glomerellales, Sordariales, Capnodiales, Rhizophlyctidales, Bacillales, Azospirillales, Sphingobacterales, Thermomicrobiales, Pyrinomonadales, Filobasidiales, Chaetothyriales and Dongiales.

Figure 9: PCA of the microbial communities' composition of soils. Blue arrows indicate the most contributive variables to data disposition in the chart: darker the blue, major the contribution. Red point (RES): soils where glyphosate-resistant biotypes of *S. halepense* were identified. Green points (SUS): soils where glyphosate-susceptible biotypes of *S. halepense* were identified. Cos2: The squared cosine, showing the importance of each component for a given observation; it is useful to find the components that are important for interpreting data; higher the cos2 value, major the contribution of the variable (Abdi, H. and Williams, L.J. (2010).

The PCA in Figure 10 shows that the soils in which glyphosate-resistant *C. canadensis* biotypes were identified are characterized by a microbial profile with the prevalence of Ktedonobacterales, Dothideomycetes (Incertae sedis), Micromonosporales, Pedosphaerales, Gaiellales, Glomerellales, Sordariales, Capnodiales, Rhizophlyctidales, Bacillales, Azospirillales and Sphingobacterales. The soils where glyphosate-susceptible *C. canadensis* biotypes were identified are typified by Thermomicrobiales, Pyrinomonadales, Filobasidiales, Chaetothyriales and Dongiales.

Figure 10: PCA of the microbial communities' composition of soils. Blue arrows indicate the most contributive variables to data disposition in the chart: darker the blue, major the contribution. Red points (RES): soils where glyphosate-resistant biotypes of *C. canadensis* were identified. Green points (SUS): soils where glyphosate-susceptible biotypes of *C. canadensis* were identified. Cos2: The squared cosine, showing the importance of each component for a given observation; it is useful to find the components that are important for interpreting data; higher the cos2 value, major the contribution of the variable (Abdi, H. and Williams, L.J. (2010).

The PCA in Figure 11 shows that the soils in which glyphosate-resistant *C. dactylon* biotypes were identified are characterized by a microbial profile with the prevalence of Thermomicrobiales, Pyrinomonadales and Filobasidiales. In the other soils where glyphosate-susceptible *C. dactylon* biotypes were identified, the microbial profile is characterized by the prevalence of Ktedonobacterales, Dothideomycetes, Micromonosporales, Pedosphaerales, Gaiellales, Glomerellales, Sordariales, Capnodiales, Rhizophlyctidales, Bacillales, Azospirillales, Spingobacterales, Pyrinomonadales, Filobasidiales, Chaetothyriales and Dongiales.

Figure 11: PCA of the microbial communities' composition of soils. Blue arrows indicate the most contributive variables to data disposition in the chart: darker the blue, major the contribution. Red point (RES): soils where glyphosate-resistant biotypes of *C. dactylon* were identified. Green points (SUS): soils where glyphosate-susceptible biotypes of *C. dactylon* were identified. Cos2: The squared cosine, showing the importance of each component for a given observation; it is useful to find the components that are important for interpreting data; higher the cos2 value, major the contribution of the variable (Abdi, H. and Williams, L.J. (2010).

Description of the most distinctive orders of bacteria, Archaea and fungi in the analyzed soils

Following, a list of the orders of bacteria, *Archaea*, and fungi that most distinguished the vineyard soils of the farms analyzed is reported, together with a brief characterization of each order and any eventual relationship found in the literature with the administration of glyphosate.

Gemmatimonadales: these bacteria are ubiquitous in agricultural soils and are adapted to arid and low moisture conditions, common features in many viticultural environments. Their adaptability suggests an important role in the resilience of viticultural soils under water stress conditions. These bacteria are involved in the phosphorus cycle and their presence has been associated with neutral pH soils (Novello et al., 2017). Recent research found that glyphosate-treated soils exhibited increased relative abundance of *Gemmatimonadetes* during the summer season. This suggests that glyphosate's impact on this bacterial group may be influenced by seasonal factors (Hudek et al., 2021).

Pedosphaerales: these bacteria are commonly found in vineyard soils, contributing to the degradation of complex polysaccharides and to organic matter turnover. Their abundance is influenced by soil moisture levels: it is higher during periods of dryness, suggesting an adaptation to stressful environments (Besze et al., 2024). A study investigating the impact of glyphosate on bacterial diversity found that glyphosate application led to an increased abundance of certain bacterial families, including Pedosphaeraceae, which belongs to the order Pedosphaerales (Grenier et al., 2023).

Rokubacterales: the abundance of these bacteria is related to several soil physicochemical parameters: soil pH, C, N and P content (Jiang et al., 2023).

Saccharomycetales: these yeasts contribute to nutrient cycling in the soil. Their presence is influenced by geographical factors and land management practices (Coller et al., 2019).

Hailangiales: these bacteria contribute to nutrient cycling in the soil and prefer cooler soil environments, suggesting that vineyard management practices can impact their populations (Coller et al., 2019).

Dothideomycetes: these fungi belong to the Ascomycota phylum. They are prevalent in vineyard soils, contributing significantly to the fungal microbiome of grapevine ecosystems. Their ecological roles encompass nutrient cycling, plant health, and interactions with other soil microorganisms. (Hendgen et al., 2018). They are reported to be significantly influenced by management practices applied in the vineyards (Blanco et al., 2024). *Dothiorella viticola* - recorded in farm 6 - is a causal agent of Botryosphaeria dieback, a grapevine trunk disease (Urbez-Torres et al., 2009). *Cladosporium* spp. and *Alternaria* spp. are associated with leaf spots and bunch rot in grapevines. (Baka & Krzywinski, 1996).

Capnodiales: these order includes saprotrophs or plant pathogens fungi. Their presence in vineyard soils is influenced by environmental factors and agricultural practices (Blanco et al., 2024). Colautti et al. (2023) reported that Capnodiales has been found in higher percentages in conventional vineyards than in organic ones.

Cyanobacterales: these bacteria are involved in soil structure maintenance and nitrogen fixation, enriching soil fertility. Their abundance is influenced by management practices, environmental conditions and stress factors (Viñas et al., 2022).

Pezizales: these fungi (Ascomycota) form ectomycorrhizal relationships with plant roots, facilitating nutrient exchange and enhancing plant health. Many Pezizales species are saprobes, decomposing organic matter and

contributing to nutrient cycling within the soil. The presence of Pezizales can serve as indicators of soil health, reflecting the impact of vineyard management practices on the soil ecosystem (Coller et al., 2019).

Myxococcales: these bacteria are able to degrade a wide range of organic materials and are known to be an integral component of the grapevine root microbiome (Dries et al., 2023).

Sphingobacteriales: these bacteria are known for their ability to degrade complex organic materials, contributing to nutrient cycling and soil health. They are affected by agricultural management practices (Calleja-Cervantes et al., 2015).

Bacillales: these bacteria are known for their abilities to promote plant growth, improve soil fertility, and act as biocontrol agents against plant pathogens. Their abundance in soils of central Europe vineyards has been reported to be affected by management practices (Šimanský et al., 2024). Certain *Bacillus* strains (i.e. *Bacillus subtilis* strain Bs-15, *Bacillus* sp. FC1) demonstrate notable tolerance to glyphosate and possess the capability to degrade it (Yu et al., 2015).

Cytophagales: these bacteria are known for their role in degrading complex organic materials into soil ecosystems. In a study examining the impact of glyphosate on bacterial communities, the abundance of species belonging to Cytophagales was reported to be not significantly changed upon glyphosate treatment (Wang et al., 2017).

Ktedonobacterales: these filamentous, spore-forming bacteria are ubiquitous in terrestrial environments, including agricultural soils. They act in the decomposition of organic matter (Yan et al., 2020). Furthermore, they have been documented to be abundant either in extreme environments or in undisturbed soils (Gangwar et al., 2024).

Micromonosporales: these bacteria are involved in organic matter decomposition and in the production of bioactive compounds, contributing to soil fertility and nutrient cycling (Yeager et al., 2017). This order includes *Micromonospora* spp. – recorded in farms 1, 2, 3 and 6 - which have practical implications in agriculture: in fact, these species are able to enhance the biomass and the overall health of plants; moreover, they produce antimicrobial compounds and degrade pathogen cell walls positions them as natural biocontrol agents against soil-borne diseases (Martínez-Hidalgo et al., 2014).

Gaiellales: these bacteria are involved in soil nutrient cycling. Their abundance has been associated with higher levels of available phosphorus in soil (Wang et al., 2024). A study investigating the impact of glyphosate-based herbicides on the rhizosphere microbiome of *Avena sativa* L. reported a decrease in the relative abundance of these bacteria in glyphosate-treated plants compared to the untreated controls (Allegrini et al., 2019). Otherwise, their abundance was recorded significantly higher in soil treated with S-metolachlor than in untreated controls (Galic et al., 2024). This suggests that the response of Gaiellales to herbicide application may vary depending on the specific herbicide and environmental context.

Glomerellales: these order of fungi includes genera such as *Colletotrichum*, which are known for their roles as plant pathogens and endophytes.

Sordariales: these fungi play essential roles in decomposing organic matter and contributing to nutrient cycling in soil ecosystems. Some studies have observed associations between Sordariomycetes, the class encompassing Sordariales, and glyphosate treatments, recording a shift in fungal community upon glyphosate administration (Schlatter et al., 2018; Jang et al., 2025).

Rhizophlyctidales: these are chytrid fungi commonly found in aquatic and soil environments, playing important roles in organic matter decomposition, specifically cellulose, hemicellulose, and pectin. This decomposition process contributes to the global carbon cycle (Letcher et al., 2006).

Azospirillales: proteobacteria known for containing *Azospirillum* spp., which are important plant-growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR). These species are notable for nitrogen fixation, phytohormone production, and beneficial interactions with plant roots. Some bacteria, including PGPR, possess EPSPS or rely on aromatic amino acid synthesis pathways that can be directly affected by glyphosate (Zobiolo et al., 2010). *Skermanella* spp. were recorded in almost all the farms investigated: they are known to act in nutrient cycles (Luo et al., 2012).

Thermomicrobiales and Pyrinomonadales: these bacteria contribute to organic matter turnover and mineralization under anaerobic or microaerophilic conditions. They are included in the Chloroflexi phylum, generally frequent in the deeper layer of agricultural soils, vineyards included (Zarraonaindia et al., 2015).

Filobasidiales: these fungi are saprotrophic or commensal, with some known as opportunistic human pathogens (i.e. *Cryptococcus* spp.). These fungi are basidiomycetous yeasts, a core part of the vineyard microbiome (Zarraonaindia et al., 2015).

Filobasidium magnum, *F. globisporum* and *F. oriense* have been recorded in many of the surveyed vineyards. Many *Filobasidium* species - particularly *F. laurentii* - have been reported to have antagonistic effects against plant pathogens (Trotel-Aziz et al., 2006).

Chaetothyriales: these fungal order comprises many species often associated with extreme environments and known for their melanized (darkly pigmented) cell walls, which can provide resistance to environmental stressors, including toxic compounds (Eisenman et al., 2012).

Dongiales: this order of fungi includes many plant pathogens (e.g., species causing leaf spots or blotches), endophytes, and saprobes. The only species found in the surveyed vineyards is *Aureobasidium pullulans*, a common epiphytic fungus present on grape berries, leaves, and vine bark, which has been recognized for its antagonistic activity against several grapevine pathogens, including *Botrytis cinerea* (gray mold) and *Penicillium* species causing bunch rot (Bozoudi et al., 2018).

Analysis of the relationship between the soil physical and chemical properties and the soil microbial composition

The correlation between each individual physical and chemical property of the soil and each bacterial and fungal order of the microbial communities surveyed in the vineyard soils was assessed using correlation tests (Spearman) computed in R (R Core Team). Only microbial taxa recording a relative abundance $\geq 2\%$ were considered.

Figure 12: corrplot of relationship between the physical and chemical properties of soils and the microbial communities surveyed in the soils of the vineyard analyzed. Blue indicates a negative correlation, red color positive correlation. The darker the color and the tinier the ellipse, the stronger the correlation is. *: significant correlation ($p < 0.05$).

The corrplot (figure 12) highlights significant associations between some soil physical-chemical properties and the relative presence of some microbial orders. In particular, some components of the soil texture and some chemical properties are positively or negatively correlated with some bacterial and fungal orders.

Furthermore, to evaluate whether soil physical and chemical properties influence the overall composition of microbial communities, a Mantel test was performed using R (R Core Team). The Mantel test does not reveal any significant influence of the soil physical-chemical properties on the microbial community composition ($r = 0.13$; p -value = 0.31).

Analysis of soil microbial diversity

For Bacteria, *Archaea* and Fungi, α -diversity was assessed at the taxonomic rank of orders by computing Margalef, Shannon, Simpson and Pielou indexes using R software (Table 2).

Table 2: list of farms with α -diversity indexes for bacteria, *Archaea* and fungi

Farm	Agricultural management	Soil management	Bacteria and <i>Archaea</i>				Fungi			
			Richness	Diversity	Dominance	Evenness	Richness	Diversity	Dominance	Evenness
1	Reg. EU 2018/848 - Organic	tillage	18,21	3,74	0,81	0,04	10,82	2,34	0,59	0,17
2	Dir. EC 2009/128	subsoil tillage	19,46	3,75	0,80	0,04	8,12	2,55	0,69	0,12
3	Reg. EU 2018/848 - Organic	spontaneous grass cover	20,17	3,81	0,80	0,04	9,78	2,45	0,63	0,15
4	Dir. EC 2009/128	subsoil tillage	20,88	3,80	0,80	0,04	11,66	2,78	0,69	0,09
5	Dir. EC 2009/128	subsoil tillage	20,88	3,83	0,80	0,04	11,45	2,53	0,63	0,15
6	Dir. EC 2009/128	tillage	18,56	3,70	0,79	0,04	9,99	2,48	0,64	0,15
7	Reg. EU 2018/848 - Organic	tillage + cover crop	26,78	3,97	0,79	0,03	9,99	2,61	0,67	0,10

The bacterial and archaeal communities showed higher average values of richness, diversity and evenness and lower average values of dominance than fungi.

Bacterial and archaeal communities' richness and diversity seem to be related to the soil management practices applied in the farms since the highest indexes' values were observed in farms 3, 4, 5 and 7, where less impactful practices were adopted (spontaneous grass cover, subsoil tillage, cover crop), while low values were recorded in farms 1 and 6, where tillage was performed. As concerns fungal communities, the highest richness values were observed in farms 4 and 5, where subsoil tillage was adopted.

The dominance and evenness indices of the bacterial, archaeal and fungal communities in the different farms do not show great variations.

Analysis of the microbial diversity of the soils investigated shows no relationship between microbial diversity indices and glyphosate application.

Conclusive remarks

To sum up, four weed species have been identified as potentially dangerous due to their ability to develop resistance to glyphosate administration in the vineyards: *E. crus-galli*, *S. halepense*, *C. canadensis* and *C. dactylon*.

The soils in which resistant biotypes of the weeds under consideration were recognized, are characterized by different microbial profiles than those in which the weeds were found to be sensitive to glyphosate.

These results allow us to make predictions, based on the microbial composition of the soil, as to whether resistant biotypes may be present in a vineyard, and since the microbial profiles are not the same for all four resistant weeds, also to understand which species are prioritized over the others.

Table 3: presence of glyphosate resistance in relation to soil microbial composition

Microbial profile	<i>Glyphosate-resistant E. crus galli</i>	<i>Glyphosate-resistant S. halepense</i>	<i>Glyphosate-resistant C. canadensis</i>	<i>Glyphosate-resistant C. dactylon</i>
Gemmatimonadales Pedosphaerales Rokubacterales Saccharomycetales Hailangiales Dothideomycetes	yes			
Ktedonobacterales Dothideomycetes Micromonosporales Pedophaerales Gaiellales		yes	yes	
Glomerellales, Sordariales, Capnodiales, Rhizophlyctidales, Bacillales, Azospirillales and Sphingobacterales			yes	
Thermomicrobiales Pyrinomonadales Filobasidiales				yes

The soil management practices applied in vineyards (e.g. tillage, reduced tillage, cover crops, etc.) appear to have a greater impact on the diversity of soil microbial communities than the glyphosate application. As a matter of fact, glyphosate can act both as a toxin and as a nutrient source: this fact may induce subtle shifts in microbial populations, favoring species capable of metabolizing glyphosate over those that cannot (Liu et al., 2018). In fact, some bacteria possess pathways that allow them to utilize glyphosate as a phosphorus source, giving them a competitive advantage in glyphosate-rich environments (Zhao et al., 2015). For example, some bacteria, including PGPR like *Azospirillum*, possess EPSPS or rely on aromatic amino acid synthesis pathways that can be directly affected by glyphosate. Otherwise, many other bacteria possess alternative pathways which make them less sensitive if compared to plants (Rainio et al., 2021).

Regarding fungi, they typically possess a different form of the EPSPS enzyme - the primary target of glyphosate - than that of plants: in fungi, this enzyme often has a multi-domain structure, leading to a more complex and variable response to glyphosate exposure. As a result, fungi may exhibit differential sensitivity to glyphosate due to this. Nevertheless, fungal communities may be indirectly affected through changes in nutrient availability, shifts in microbial competition, or the impact of surfactants present in glyphosate formulations (Tall et al., 2022).

In addition, the physical and chemical properties of soils did not seem to directly influence the overall composition of microbial communities. Rather, it appears that each microbial consortium is adapted to its specific pedological environment, which in turn seems to favor the development of weeds able to survive the application of chemical control.

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